

MULTILINGUISM, PLURILINGUISM AND BILINGUISM

Isanova Zebuniso Shavkatovna,

PhD student of Uzbekistan State University of world languages, Tashkent
Uzbekistan

Khaitova Muattar Adkhamovna

English teacher at the academic lyceum of the Uzbekistan State University of
World Languages

E-mail: zebunisoisanova7@gmail.com

Tel: +99833 3588086

Annotation: This article analyzes the differences between plurilinguism within multilingualism and concepts such as multilingualism, bilingualism and polyglot.

Key words: Multilingualism, plurilinguism, bilingualism, monolingualism, polyglot

Defined as complex connections between linguistic competencies and languages, the term plurilingualism is neologism. However, theories about multilingualism appeared much earlier in linguistics.

E.M. Veretshagin, Haugen E., Sherba L.O., Džusupov M. others have done research on multilingualism¹. Zarate G., Cramsch S., Moore D., Prasad G., E. Piccardo, A. Galante and others have done research on plurilingualism².

¹ Верещагин Е. М. Пассивный и активный билингвизм и языковое контактирование. — В кн.: Материалы конф. «Актуальные вопросы современного языка кознания и лингвистическое наследие Е. Д. Поливанова». Самарканд, Изд-во Самарк. ун-та, 1964, с. 269—270.

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Щерба Л. В. О понятии смешения языков. — Избранные работы по языкознанию и фонетике. Л., Изд-во Ленингр. ун-та, 1958, т. 1.

Джусупов М. Межязыковое и межкультурное контактирование: понятие, слово, психообраз, интерференция // *Филологические науки НДВШ. М.*, 2016. С. 22—34.

² Zarate, G., Levy, D., & Kramsch, C. (2008). *Précis du plurilinguisme et du pluriculturalisme*. Paris, France: Contemporary Publishing International SARL.

Moore, D., & Gajo, L. (2009). Introduction: French voices on plurilingualism and pluriculturalism—theory, significance, and perspectives. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 6(2), 137–153.

Prasad, G. (2014). Portraits of plurilingualism in a French international school in Toronto: Exploring the role of visual methods to access students' representations of their linguistically diverse identities. *Canadian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 17(1), 51–77. p52

The evolving multilingual paradigm suggests that people develop a network of skills and practices that several languages use for different purposes in interconnected different contexts. Multilingualism and the use of language are viewed by people as a cross-linked system in selected contexts based on their own needs.

Multilingualism (polylingualism) is the use of several languages within a certain social society. There are two types of multilingualism: 1) national and 2) individual (equally fluent use by the individual in at least three languages each day, as opposed to foreign languages). In the first, it is understood that two or more languages are valid in a multinational territory. National multilingualism is observed in multinational Countries (Russia, India, Nigeria, etc. In multilingualism, different language forms (literary languages, dialects, social and professional jargons, etc. Multilingualism in practice is usually done in the form of bilingualism³.

The second type is the knowledge and use of two or more languages according to the needs of the individual.

Related to multilingualism, concepts such as bilingualism, multilingualism and plurilingualism differ from each other.

While plurilingualism and multilingualism are given synonymously, there are conflicting opinions around these two terms. Plurilingual is a person who is able to communicate in several languages (with varying levels of skills).

First of all, referring to the etymology of origin of the words multilingual, plurilingual and polyglot . "polyglot" is derived from Greek and the oldest of the terms cited.

Webster's Dictionary records the first use of the word polyglot in English as early as 1645⁴. When separating a compound word, it means multiple languages.

³ Словарь социолингвистических терминов. М., 2006. 312 с. Ответственный редактор: доктор филологических наук В.Ю. Михальченко Авторы: к.ф.н. В.А. Кожемякина, Н.Г. Колесник, д.ф.н. Т.Б. Крючкова, к.ф.н. О.С. Парфенова, к.ф.н. Ю.В. Трушкова, при участии к.ф.н. А.Н. Биткеевой и к.ф.н. М.А. Горячевой

⁴ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/polyglot>

The word Multilingual comes from Latin and was first used in 1838. The compound word means multiple languages.

Plurilingualism is a neologism, given to multilingualism as a synonym in Webster's dictionary as well. Plurilingualism is first equivalent to multilingualism when referring to multilingual communities in which several languages are spoken in society. However, it is necessary to distinguish plurilingualism in order to distinguish between personality and society.

Most scholars (Marshall, Moor, 2018;)⁵ recognize plurilingualism and multilingualism as one concept, but they distinguish plurilingualism as being focused on the individual and multilingualism as being focused on society.

Plurilingualism has been used to pay attention to the individual in the interaction of languages, multilingualism describes as the social connection of many languages D.Koste, D.Moore and g.Zarate⁶.

To qualify in a single language, four skills are needed, which are reading, writing, speaking and listening. Communication has another ability, the ability to switch between languages, and it is a skill of multilingualism.

A multilingual is a person who speaks different languages. A multilingual can have a high level of reading, writing, speaking, listening and comprehension skills as well as dialectal proficiency. A multilingual acquires languages through the social environment (e.g. parents' languages, bilingual education, long-term residence abroad, international work, etc.).

A polyglot is someone who can communicate verbally in many languages, by talking to others and listening to them. Usually this person has skills in oral dialects. Polyglot learns languages by himself with interest.

⁵ Marshall, S. & Moore, D. (2018). Plurilingualism amid the panoply of lingualisms: addressing critiques and misconceptions in education. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 15(1), 19–34

⁶ Coste, Daniel & Moore, Danièle & Zarate, Geneviève. (2009). Plurilingual and Pluricultural Competence. *Studies Towards a Common European Framework of Reference for Language Learning and Teaching*. Reference Studies for the Council of Europe.

Plurilingual - does not mean that a person knows many languages perfectly, but can replace their skills in several languages with one when the situation requires it.

If a person can speak one language, understand another, and can easily switch between languages at the required time, this is considered plurilingual competent.

Monolingual	(Greek monos - One, only + latin. lingua-language) language. A person who speaks only one language. Monolingualism refers only to the knowledge of one's native language - one's own ethnic or another concept of monolingualism: 1) individuals; 2) groups of people; 3) language community.	Словарь лингвистических терминов: И зд. 5-е, испр- е и дополн. — Назрань: Изд- во "Пилигрим". Т.В. Жеребило. 2010.
bilingual	Bilingual (bi-two,+lingua-language) is human bilingualism, bilingualism. Bilingualism 1. The ability of an individual or group to use bilingualism as an alternative 2. The realisation of the ability to use two languages as an alternative; the practice of alternative communication in two languages. There is a narrow and a broad understanding of bilingualism. In a narrow sense, it is understood as a moderately fluent command of the mother tongue and non-native languages, and in a broad sense, as a relative knowledge of the second language and the ability to communicate in it in certain areas of communication.....	АЗИМОВ Э. Г., ЩУКИН А. Н. "Новый словарь методических терминов и понятий (теория и практика обучения языкам)." – М.: Издательство ИКАР, 2009. – 448 с.
Multilingualism	Multilingualism (multilingualism). The coexistence of a single multilingual state in the framework of international associations of different countries or as an attribute of national culture. 2. The general rule in the European educational	АЗИМОВ Э. Г., ЩУКИН А. Н. "Новый словарь методических терминов и

	system is that it requires a modern person to know two foreign languages in addition to his or her mother tongue. M. indicates that a person knows several languages. M is also used when referring to a multilingual city or country. M. to strengthen the diversity of languages in the education system, encouraging the learning of other languages, is achieved by.	понятий (теория и практика обучения языкам).” – М.: Издательство ИКАР, 2009. – 448 с.
Plurilingual	the <u>ability</u> to use <u>skills</u> in a <u>number</u> of <u>different languages</u> for <u>effective communication</u> . Plurilingualism is one of the <u>goals</u> of the <u>CEFR</u> .	https://www.macmi.ru/dictionary.com
Polyglot	(poly...+ Greek glotta-language) is a multilingual expert. Naori Takeda, who was born and raised in Japan, is a fluent polyglot because she is fluent in Japanese, Italian and Spanish.	Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли лўғати.”Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат миллий нашриёти. Тошкент 2020

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